

The Effect of Work Discipline, Work Environment and Adversity Quotient on Performance of Personnel of Satsamapta Unit Polres Serang City

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Abstract:- This research analyzes the impact of discipline work, environmental work, and adversity quotient on personnel performance in police force unit Sasamapta in Serang City. The study was quantitative research with a sample of 59 respondents who are personnels of Unit SatsamaptaSerang City Police. Method data collection used in a study was a questionnaire with data analysis using SPSS 25 software. The findings were that (1) Discipline work and (2) Environment work did not affect the performance of the police of Satsamapta Serang City. (3) There is a positive and significant effect on adversity quotient toward personnel performance. (4) There are influence positive and significant discipline work, environment discipline work and adversity quotient, simulant has an effect toward personnel performance. The highest impact on personnel performance was the adversity quotient. Management above must notice the adversity quotient of every person who appreciates the member to boost their innovation. Then give Support to personnel who want change and learn from error because the adversity quotient is vital for increasing the performance of Satsamapta police force in Serang City.

Keywords:- DisciplineWork, Environment Work, Adversity Quotient, Personnel Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Police Organization, Banten Regional, was under the National Police in the Police Nationals. Based on the performance report of the Banten Regional Police in 2020, the Banten Police have decreasing performance. There are key performance indicators that are not achieved or do not match the targets that have been set in national standards. Some of the indicators that were not achieved, among others, were related to member discipline violations, a decrease in criminal acts committed by the member, and violations of the code of ethics by a personnel police officer. In 2020, set a 5% reduction target for reducing criminal offenses committed by the Indonesian National Police. However, in reality, there has been an increase in personnel committing criminal offenses with a realization of -30%, so the target for reducing crimes committed by police personnel is not achieved.

Violations of criminal acts committed by the Banten Police and its ranks in 2019 were ten officers, and in 2020 as many as 13 officers, increasing criminal offenses committed by personnel, which caused the set target not to be achieved [1].Violations of the code of ethics were committed by 46 personnel Banten Police officers in 2019. Increase to 62 in 2020. Based on information from the National Police force, the person who commits disciplinary violations that lead to violations of criminal acts and the code of ethics is dominated by personnel at the Serang City Police officer, the data is as follows:

No	Satker	Year	
		2019	2020
1	Serang Police	2	1
2	Cilegon Police	-	1
3	Pandeglang Police	-	1
3	Lebak Police	2	2
4	Tangerang Police	2	3
5	City Attack Police	4	5

Table 1: Data violations of criminal acts committed by personnel police officer

Data source: Banten Regional Police Agency Performance Report 2020

Based on the data above, it can be concluded that the city attack police unit dominates personnel violations. A previous study has conducted interviews with 8 (eight) personnel of the Serang City Police Satsamapta who have a low level of discipline. The eight personnel with track records committed disciplinary violations such as dissertation (not coming in for 14 consecutive days), using drugs, and always being late to work. They explained that, in principle, they knew what they were doing was wrong because of the work environment.

No	Statement	STS (%)	TS (%)	N (%)	S (%)	SS (%)	TOTAL (%)
1	I am never late according to the working hours that have been set by my agency.	33.3	66.7				100
2	I never leave the office for personal matters after work hours	33.3	60	6.7			100
3	I always obey the policy rules that have been set	20	66.7		13.3		100
Total Average		28.8	64.4	2.2	4.4		

Table 2: Results of Pre-Survey Work Discipline

Source: Results of the Work Discipline Survey at the Serang City Police Satsamapta Unit, February 2021

No	Statement	STS (%)	TS (%)	N (%)	S (%)	SS (%)	TOTAL (%)
1	The working atmosphere at my workplace is harmonious and pleasant	26.7	73.7				100
2	The facilities at my workplace are adequate so that it does not hinder me from working	40	53.3	6.7			100
3	I can concentrate well because my work environment is calm and clean	40	53.3	6.7			100
Total Average		35.5	59.9	4.4			

Table 3: Pre-Survey Results of Work Environment

Source: Results of the Work Environment Survey at the Serang City Police Samapta Unit, February 2021

No	Statement	STS (%)	TS (%)	N (%)	S (%)	SS (%)	TOTAL (%)
1	The difficulties that befell me will not make me fall into despair	26.7	66.7		6.7		100
2	I will be responsible for any mistakes that are I did and will fix it	26.7	66.7		6.7		100
3	Today the task assigned to me feels difficult, but I'm sure this feeling doesn't last long	33.3	66.7				100

Table 4: Results of Pre-Survey Power fight

Source: Results of the Work Environment Survey at the Serang City Police Samapta Unit, February 2021

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Discipline Work

Wiratama & Sintasih [2] explain that work discipline is a management action that increases the awareness and motivation of its members to comply with regulations and voluntarily by applying social norms set by the organization or company. Based on Article 1 of Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 2 of 2003 [3], Regarding the rules of the state police, discipline is declared as simple obedience and obedience to the rules of the state police of the Republic of Indonesia. Disciplinary rules for members of the police are a set of norms designed to promote, enforce, and maintain order in the lives of members of the Indonesian National Police.

B. Environment Work

The work environment is everything that can affect the performance of the tasks performed. Siagian [4] claims that the work environment is where personnels do their daily work. Difficult situations can affect a person's ability to solve problems.

C. Adversity Quotient

Stoltz in Budiani [5] states that adversity Quotient is the ability to face everyday obstacles and difficulties, overcome the problems, and stay focused on the goal, regardless of the obstacles around them. Adversity Quotient is a person's ability to persevere in pursuing a dream.

D. Personnel Performance

According to Sinambela [6], personnel performance is the ability of an personnel to perform specific skills. Performance results from individual work of expertise to complete the tasks and workloads set by the organization. The difference between authority and performance responsibility varies according to the authority of each personnel.

Fig. 1: Research Framework

E. Research Design

This study uses quantitative methods. The variables studied were Work Discipline (X1), Work Environment (X2) and Adversity Quotient (X3) on Performance (Y) of the Serang City Police force unit.

F. Population

Sugiyono [7] explained that the population is a distinct object area determined by the researcher for analysis. The population selected is the members of the Satsamapta Police Force of Serang City.

G. Samples

The sample used as respondents in this study were 59 personnel of the Serang City Satsamapta Political Force Unit.

H. Methods of Data Analysis

The data collection technique is a questionnaire (questionnaire) in the form of closed questions. In this study, the scale used is divided into four parts, namely four that reveal performance, work discipline, work environment, and adversity quotient.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Characteristics Respondent

Of the 59 respondents, most were male, 55 people (93.2%), while the respondents were female, four people (6.8%). In addition, most of the respondents had a High school graduate level, which is 35 people (59.3%), then 33 respondents with bachelor level (37.3%) and master only two people (3.4%) with respondents working for 16 – 20 years old. Therefore, respondents with a working experience < 5 years were eight people (13.6%), 5-10 years were 16 people (27.1%), and 11-15 years were 14 people (23.7%).

B. Validity Test

The number of respondents in this study was 59 respondents. From the number of respondents, it can be seen that the magnitude of the r table is 0.2162 (df = n-2 = 59-2 = 57) with an error rate of 5%. So that the data in table 5 is obtained as follows:

Variable	Statement	R count	R table	Information
	1	0,469	0,2162	Valid
	2	0,532	0,2162	Valid
	3	0,537	0,2162	Valid
	4	0,371	0,2162	Valid
	5	0,455	0,2162	Valid
	6	0,573	0,2162	Valid
	7	0,743	0,2162	Valid
Discipline Work	8	0,598	0,2162	Valid
	9	0,622	0,2162	Valid
	10	0,703	0,2162	Valid
	11	0,582	0,2162	Valid
	12	0,561	0,2162	Valid
	13	0,768	0,2162	Valid
	14	0,751	0,2162	Valid
	15	0,543	0,2162	Valid
	16	0,485	0,2162	Valid
	17	0,448	0,2162	Valid
	18	0,437	0,2162	Valid
	19	0,362	0,2162	Valid
	20	0,554	0,2162	Valid
Environment Work	21	0,563	0,2162	Valid
	22	0,474	0,2162	Valid
	23	0,484	0,2162	Valid
	24	0,467	0,2162	Valid
	25	0,752	0,2162	Valid
	26	0,802	0,2162	Valid
	27	0,388	0,2162	Valid
	28	0,53	0,2162	Valid
	29	0,589	0,2162	Valid
	30	0,63	0,2162	Valid
	31	0,612	0,2162	Valid
	32	0,493	0,2162	Valid
Adversity Quotient	33	0,644	0,2162	Valid
	34	0,69	0,2162	Valid
	35	0,682	0,2162	Valid
	36	0,337	0,2162	Valid
	37	0,456	0,2162	Valid
	38	0,546	0,2162	Valid
	39	0,415	0,2162	Valid
	40	0,648	0,2162	Valid
	41	0,622	0,2162	Valid
	42	0,309	0,2162	Valid
	43	0,802	0,2162	Valid
	44	0,784	0,2162	Valid
Personnel Performance	45	0,822	0,2162	Valid
	46	0,828	0,2162	Valid
	47	0,819	0,2162	Valid
	48	0,74	0,2162	Valid
	49	0,821	0,2162	Valid
	50	0,812	0,2162	Valid

Table 5: Validity Test Results Study

Source of processed data (2022)

On the table on show that all statement items declared valid because have value of r count > r Table (0.2162).

C. Reliability Test

Table 6, it shows that all variables have Cronbach's Alpha values greater than 0.60. The four variable instruments meet the reliable requirements so that they can be used in research questionnaires in collecting research data.

Variable	value	Criteria	Conclusion
Discipline Work	,859	> 0.60	Reliable
Environment Work	,721	> 0.60	Reliable
Adversity Quotient	,784	> 0.60	Reliable
Personnel Performance	,748	> 0.60	Reliable

Table 6: Reliability Test Results

Source of processed data (2022)

D. Normality Test

		Work Discipline	Work environment	Power struggle	Performance
N		59	59	59	59
Normal Parameters	mean	72.66	46.02	63.59	45.34
	Std. Deviation	8,792	2,467	6,744	3.985
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	,224	,112	,233	,261
	Positive	,202	,098	,171	,129
	negative	-,224	-,112	-,233	-,261
Test Statistics		,224	,112	,233	,261
asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		,000 ^c	,061 ^c	,000 ^c	,000 ^c

Table 7: One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

Source of processed data (2022)

- a. Test distribution is Normal.
- b. Calculated from data.
- c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.

Table 7 shows the Asymp Sig value of work discipline, fighting power, and performance <0.05, then the work environment Asymp Sig value > 0.05, it can be concluded that the data that is usually distributed is only the work environment variable. Because there are data that are not

normally distributed, a Z score test is performed to remove outliers. Outliers are observations or data with values that differ from other observations and appear in extreme values. Data observations with a z score < -0.25 or a z score > 2.5 will be categorized as outliers.

No	Z Mean Discipline Work	Z Mean Environment Work	Z Mean Power fight	Z Mean Performance
1	0.83475	-1,22294	0.94993	0.16586
2	0.37978	-1,22294	0.94993	0.16586
3	-0.98512	-0.81758	-0.3846	-0.08506
4	0.83475	-0.81758	0.35688	0.16586
5	0.83475	-1,22294	0.94993	0.16586
6	0.83475	-1,22294	0.94993	0.16586
7	-2.46376	-1,22294	-1.71892	-1.84148
8	0.37978	1.61456	0.35688	1.16953
9	-0.18893	-0.00687	0.80172	-0.33598
10	0.1523	-0.41223	0.80172	1.16953
11	0.83475	-0.81758	0.35688	0.16586
12	0.83475	-0.00687	0.94993	0.16586
13	-0.53015	-0.41223	-1.71892	-1,33965
14	-1,32634	1.2092	-0.53281	0.41678
15	0.37978	1.61456	0.94993	1.16953
16	0.83475	0.39849	0.94993	0.16586
17	0.83475	0.80384	0.94993	0.16586
18	-0.07519	-0.41223	-0.82923	0.16586
19	0.83475	0.80384	0.94993	0.16586
20	0.83475	1.61456	0.94993	0.16586
21	0.37978	-0.41223	0.35688	1.16953
22	-0.87138	-1.6283	0.06025	-1.08873
23	0.1523	-0.00687	0.94993	-0.08506
24	0.37978	-0.41223	0.35688	1.16953
25	0.37978	0.39849	0.35688	0.16586
26	0.37978	0.39849	0.6533	1.16953
27	-0.30267	1.2092	-0.82923	0.16586
28	0.83475	-0.00687	0.20867	-0.08506
29	-0.98512	0.80384	-1.42249	-1,59057
30	-1,44008	-2.03365	-1.12586	-1.84148
31	0.60726	-0.81758	-0.3846	0.6677
32	0.60726	-0.00687	0.94993	1.16953
33	0.37978	-0.00687	0.94993	0.16586

34	0.83475	1.2092	0.35688	1.16953
35	-0.87138	-1,22294	-1.12586	-1,59057
36	-1.2126	-0.41223	-2.31197	-1,33965
37	-0.87138	-1.6283	-1.5707	-1.84148
38	0.37978	0.39849	0.94993	0.16586
39	-1.66757	0.39849	0.94993	0.91862
40	0.83475	-0.00687	0.94993	0.16586
41	-1.09886	-0.81758	-1.12586	-2.84516
42	-0.64389	-2.03365	-1.71892	-0.33598
43	0.37978	-1,22294	0.35688	1.16953
44	-1.09886	-1,22294	-1.42249	-1.84148
45	-1,32634	-0.81758	-1,27407	1.16953
46	-4,16988	1.2092	0.35688	1.16953
47	-0.30267	0.39849	-1.12586	-1.08873
48	-0.07519	0.39849	-0.08796	0.6677
49	0.83475	1.2092	0.94993	0.16586
50	0.83475	0.39849	0.94993	0.16586
51	0.60726	1.2092	0.35688	0.16586
52	-0.30267	-0.00687	-1.12586	-1.84148
53	0.72101	0.39849	-2.01555	1.16953
54	0.72101	0.80384	0.94993	0.16586
55	-0.41641	0.80384	-0.82923	1.16953
56	0.83475	0.80384	0.35688	0.41678
57	0.83475	1.2092	-1.12586	-1.08873
58	0.83475	1.2092	0.35688	0.16586
59	0.83475	1.61456	0.94993	0.16586

Table 8: Outlier Univariate Test

Based on table 8, it was found that the data outliers in the work discipline variable were 46 had a z score of -4.16988 < -0.25, and the performance variable sample

number 41 had a z score of -2.84516 < -0.25, then deletion was carried out on sample number 41. and no. 46 so that for further testing using 57 initially 59 samples.

E. Multipolarity Test

	Model	Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	X1 (Work Discipline)	,529	1,889
	X2 (Work Environment)	,852	1.174
	X3 (Fighting Power)	.563	1,776

a. Dependent Variable: Y (Performance)

Table 9: Table of Multicollinearity Test Results

Table 9 shows that the Tolerance and VIF values for work discipline are 0.529 and 1.889, the Tolerance and VIF values for the work environment are 0.852 and 1.174, and the Tolerance and VIF values for fighting power are 0.563 and 1.776. Because the three independent variables have

tolerance values above 0.10 and VIF values below 10, the three independent variables do not experience symptoms of multicollinearity between independent variables in the regression model, so they can be used to predict the dependent variable.

F. Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Processed data source with SPSS version , 24.0 (2022)

Figure 2 shows that the data (dots) are spread evenly above and below the zero line, do not gather in one place, and do not form a specific pattern so that it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity problem.

G. Analysis of Regression

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1,307	,776		1,684	,098
	X1 (Work Discipline)	,141	,122	,174	1,156	,253
	X2 (Work Environment)	,270	,178	,180	1.516	,135
	X3 (Fighting Power)	,297	,112	,387	2,658	,010

Table 10: Results of multiple linear analysis

Source of data processed with SPSS version, 24.0 (2022).

a. Dependent Variable: Y (Performance)

$$Y = 1.307 + 0.141X1 + 0.270X2 + 0.297X3$$

$$Y = 1.307 + 0.141X1 + 0.270X2 + 0.297X3$$

Based on the results of the multiple linear regression equation above, it can be analyzed as follows:

- The constant of 1.307 states that if all independent variables (work discipline, work environment, and fighting power) are considered constant or have a value of 0, the personnel performance will be 1.307.
- The regression coefficient of work discipline (X1) of 0.141 has a positive value which means it has a positive influence if work discipline increases by 1. In contrast, if other variables (work environment and fighting power) are considered constant or worth 0, then the personnel performance has increased by 0.141.

- The regression coefficient of the work environment (X2) of 0.270 is positive, which means it has a positive influence if the work environment increases by 1. In contrast, other variables (work discipline and fighting power) are considered constant; then, the personnel performance has increased by 0.270.
- The regression coefficient of fighting power (X3) of 0.297 has a positive value which means it has a positive influence so that if fighting power increases by 1. At the same time, other variables (work discipline and work environment) are considered constant, and personnel performance has increased by 0.297.

a. Testing for Multiple Variables at a Time (Test f)

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2,822	3	,941	10,220	,000 ^b
	Residual	4,879	53	,092		
	Total	7,701	56			

Table 11: F Test Results

a. Dependent Variable: Y (Performance)

b. Predictors: (Constant), X3 (Strength), X2 (Work Environment), X1 (Work Discipline)

The calculated F value is 10.220 with a significance value (Sig.) of 0.000, so there is a significant effect of work discipline, work environment, and fighting power on the

performance of personnel Satsamapta Police force at the Serang City.

H. Testing for Partial Variables (t-Test)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	1,307	,776		1,684	,098
	X1 (Work Discipline)	,141	,122	,174	1,156	,253
	X2 (Work Environment)	,270	,178	,180	1.516	,135
	X3 (Fighting Power)	,297	,112	,387	2,658	,010

Table 12: t test results

a. Dependent Variable: Y (Performance)

Processed data source with SPSS version , 24.0 (2022).

$$Y = 1.307 + 0.141X1 + 0.270X2 + 0.297X3$$

The multiple linear regression equation above shows that the independent variable that has the most influence on personnel performance is the fighting power variable with a regression coefficient of 0.297, then the work environment

variable with a regression coefficient of 0.270, and finally the work discipline variable with a regression coefficient of 0.141.

I. Test of Coefficient of Determination

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,605 ^a	,366	,331	,30341

Table 13: Coefficient Results Determination

a. Predictors: (Constant), X3 (Strength), X2 (Work Environment), X1 (Work Discipline)

b. Dependent Variable: Y (Performance)

a) Work Discipline Affects Performance

The test results on the first hypothesis obtained a significance value (Sig.) of 0.253, which is a significance value (0.253) > 0.05, indicating that work discipline does not affect the performance of the Satsamapta Polres Serang Kota personnel.

b) Work Environment Affects Performance

The test results on the second hypothesis that the work environment has no significant effect on personnel performance. Based on the t-test, the significance value (Sig.) is 0.135, which is the significance value (0.135) > 0.05.

c) Fighting Power Affects Performance

The result of the third test is that fighting power has a significant effect on personnel performance. Based on the t-test, the significance value (Sig.) is 0.010, where the significance value (0.010) < 0.05, then H3 is accepted, meaning that there is a significant influence on fighting power on the performance of the Satsamapta Polres Serang Kota personnel.

d) D. Work Discipline, Work Environment, and Fighting Power affect Personnel Performance

The results showed that the R-value of the coefficient of determination (R²) in Table 4.15 was 0.366. The means that 36.6% of personnel performance is

influenced by work discipline, work environment, and fighting power together. In comparison, the remaining 63.4% is influenced by other variables outside the independent variables studied in this study.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Work discipline and work environment do not affect the performance of SamaptaPolresSerang City personnel. There is a positive and significant influence of fighting power on the performance of the SamaptaPolresSerang City Personnel. In addition, there is a positive and significant influence of work discipline, work environment, and fighting spirit on the performance of the SamaptaPolresSerang City personnel. The factor that affects the highest performance is fighting power; it is recommended that agencies pay attention to the fighting power of each person by giving appreciation to members who want to innovate, then providing support to personnel who want to change and learn from mistakes, because this fighting power has an essential factor to improve performance personnel Satsamapta Police force Serang City.

V. RECOMMENDATION

It is expected to observe and research further the problems contained in the SamaptaPolresSerang City in particular and other objects in general by adding other variables such as training, leadership, competence, and leadership style.

REFERENCES

- [1.] PPB Praja ,*Agency Performance Report Banten Government* , vol. 7, no. 1. 2020, pp. 37–72.
- [2.] Sintaasih and Wiratama , “ Influence Leadership , Training , and Discipline Work Against Personnel Performance Pdam Tirta Mangutama Regency Badung , " *Journal Management , Business Strategy and Entrepreneurship* , vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 126–134, 2013.
- [3.] R. Indonesia, *Regulation Government Republic of Indonesia Number 2 Year 2003* , vol. 105, no. 3. 2003, pp. 129–133.
- [4.] SP Siagian , “ Management Source Power Humans ," *Islamic Thought in Malaysia: History and Schools* , vol. 20, no. 5, pp. 40–3, 2019.
- [5.] M. Santi Budiani , S. Psi, M. Psi, N. Wayan, S. Puspitadewi , and OP Mulyana , “ The Relationship Between Adversity Quotient And Self-Efficacy With Job Crafting In Working Women With The Work From Home (Wfh) System The Relationship Between Adversity Quotient And Self-Efficacy With Job Crafting In Women Working With Work From Home (Wfh) System,” vol. 13, no. 01, pp. 27–38, 2022.
- [6.] LijanPoltakSinambela ,*Personnel performance theory measurement and implications* . Yogyakarta: Graha Science 11, 2018.
- [7.] P. Sugiyono ,*Method study business : approach quantitative , qualitative , combined , and R & D* . CV. Alfabeta : Bandung, 2017.